

“ HOW CAN WE USE THE PRESENT CONTINUOUS?”

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Annotation: This article discusses the construction of the present continuous tense,how it is used,and in which cases we cannot use this tense.

Key words: present continuous,positive-negative meaning,V+_ing,now,at present.

What is the present continuous?

The present continuous tense is grammatical tense that can be used to describe when an action happened,or may happen.You can use it to describe both events that are happening in the present -right now,while you are talking about something,or in the future-something that may or will happen later on.

You use the present continuous by using the present form of the verb "be" + the present participle of a verb:

Positive: S+am,is,are+ V+_ing. (I am working now)

Negative:S+am,is,are +not+ V+_ing (I'm not working now)

Question:am,is,are+S+V+_ing? (Are you working now?)

In this situation we often use the present continuous:

1.Thing that are happening now:

You can use the present continuous to describe immediate events taking place in the current moment:

e.g."She is eating dinner right now and cannot answer the phone".

You can also use it in the same way for the negative form:

e.g. "They're not watching TV at the moment".

2. We use the present continuous when we talk about changing situation:

e.g. "The population of the world is rising very fast"

3. When describing something that will take place in the future, the present continuous tense can be used when you are discussing something that is already discussed or planned ahead:

e.g. "Ann is going to a new school next term"

"Tom is flying to Moscow tomorrow"

4. Temporary events:

For longer actions that may be taking place for a temporary period only, you can use the present continuous tense to describe them. It can be used for any temporary situation, no matter how long or short it is.

e.g. "He's studying a new language at the moment"

5. A new pattern or habit:

A really interesting way of using the present continuous tense is to describe events or actions that are new and different from events in the past. In this case, the tense can be used to highlight the contrast between the old and new.

e.g. "These days, people are writing emails a lot less than they used to a few years ago"

It can also be used to describe a regular habit that someone has - whether it is a good habit, or a bad one!

e.g. "You're always running late with all your deadlines!".

In this situations we don't use present continuous:

1. We don't normally use the continuous with stative verbs.

Stative verbs include:

- **verbs of thinking and feeling:**

believe, dislike, know, love, hate, prefer, understand

- **verbs of senses:**

appear, feel, look, seem, smell, sound, taste

With this verbs you use the **present simple** tense instead.

e.g."A loaf of bread costs £1.50".

You do not say "A loaf of bread is costing £1.50".

How do we spell the Present continuous tense?

We make the present continuous tense by adding **-ing** to the base verb.

Normally it is simple:**-ing**

But sometimes we have to change the word a little.Perhaps we double the last letter,or we drop a letter.

Basic rule:Just add **-ing** to the base verb: e.g. work+**ing**= working

Exception: 1.If the base verb ends in consonant + stressed vowel+ consonant,double the last letter: e.g. stop+**ing**= stopping

2.Consonant+ -e and add **-ing** = make+**ing**=making

Key words of the present continuous:

Now,at present,at the moment,right now

I am reading a book **at the moment.**

Nowadays,these day

Tom isn't smoking **these days.**

Cyrrrently,for the being time

Day after day,week after week

For now,continually,constantly

In conclusion,the topic of the present continuous tense in English is very comprehensive.In particular,this article briefly touched on how the present continuous tense is used and formed.I believe that this information will serve as a great source of knowledge for everyone.

References:

- 1.English grammar: Muhammad G'aprov,Robiya Qosimova
Toshkent "Turon-Iqbol" 2019
- 2.Raymond Murphy: "Turkestan" Publishing House,2011
"ART FLEX"Publishing House,2020
- 3."EN Smart plus" O.Uraev.